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METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING INTEGRATED LANGUAGE SKILLS OF FUTURE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. The integration of digital tools into foreign language teacher education has become important for preparing future educators for the developing demands of modern classrooms. This article performs the methodology for developing integrated language skills—listening, speaking, reading, and writing—among pre-service foreign language teachers using digital technologies. Through a mixed-methods approach, this study analyses the effectiveness of digital platforms, artificial intelligence (AI), gamification, and immersive technologies in fostering both linguistic proficiency and pedagogical competence. The article states that incorporating digital tools enhances teacher preparedness, increases engagement, and facilitates innovative teaching strategies.

Key words: a mixed-methods approach, digital technologies, integrated language skills, methodology, interactive and adaptive approaches

RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA BO‘LAJAK CHET TILLARI O‘QITUVCHILARING INTEGRALLASHGAN TIL KO‘NIKMALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH METODOLOGIYASI

Annotatsiya. Chet tillari o‘qituvchilarini tayyorlash jarayoniga raqamli texnologiyalarni integratsiya qilish zamonaviy sinflarning o‘zgaruvchan talablariga

moslashish uchun muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Ushbu maqolada kelajakdagi chet tili o'qituvchilarida integratsiyalashgan til ko'nikmalarini—tinglash, gapirish, o'qish va yozishni—raqamli vositalar yordamida rivojlantirish metodologiyasi o'rganiladi. Tadqiqot aralash usullar (mixed-methods) yondashuvi asosida olib borilib, raqamli platformalar, sun'iy intellekt (AI), gamifikatsiya va immersiv texnologiyalarning lingvistik mahorat hamda pedagogik kompetensiyani shakllantirishdagi samaradorligi tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada raqamli vositalardan foydalanish o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash jarayonini yaxshilashi, ishtirokchilarning faolligini oshirishi va innovatsion ta'lim strategiyalarini rivojlantirishga yordam berishi haqida ma'lumotlar yoritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: aralash usullar yondashuvi, raqamli texnologiyalar, integratsiyalashgan til ko'nikmalari, metodologiya, interaktiv va moslashuvchan yondashuvlar.

МЕТОДИКА ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ КОМПЛЕКСНЫХ ЯЗЫКОВЫХ УМЕНИЙ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА НА ОСНОВЕ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

Аннотация. Интеграция цифровых технологий в образование учителей иностранных языков стала необходимой для подготовки будущих педагогов к меняющимся требованиям современных классов. В этой статье рассматривается методология развития интегрированных языковых навыков — аудирования, говорения, чтения и письма — среди будущих учителей иностранных языков с использованием цифровых инструментов. В этом исследовании с использованием смешанных методов изучается эффективность цифровых платформ, искусственного интеллекта (ИИ), геймификации и технологий погружения в развитие как лингвистических навыков, так и педагогической компетентности. В статье указывается, что внедрение цифровых инструментов повышает готовность

учителей, увеличивает вовлеченность и способствует инновационным стратегиям обучения.

Ключевые слова: смешанный подход, цифровые технологии, интегрированные языковые навыки, методология, интерактивные и адаптивные подходы.

The role of digital technology in foreign language education has increased significantly over the past two decades, shifting traditional teaching methodologies toward more interactive and adaptive approaches. As globalization proceeds to increase the need for multilingual communication, foreign language teachers must possess not only strong linguistic proficiency but also the ability to integrate digital tools effectively in their classrooms.

Integrated language skills—listening, speaking, reading, and writing—are fundamental for both learners and educators. However, conventional teacher training programs often don't succeed to incorporate digital competencies, leaving pre-service teachers unprepared for contemporary teaching challenges. Digital technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI), learning management systems (LMS), virtual reality (VR), and gamification, present innovative ways to develop these skills while enhancing teaching methodologies[1,2].

This study aims to create a methodological framework for developing integrated language skills in future foreign language teachers using digital technologies. A mixed-methods research design was used to evaluate the impact of digital technologies on the development of integrated language skills. The study included qualitative and quantitative approaches, including experimental interventions, surveys, and interviews with pre-service foreign language teachers[2].

Digital tools significantly developed listening and speaking skills in the experimental group. AI-powered applications such as Duolingo, Speechling, and Google AI-powered speech recognition gave the opportunity for the participants to practice pronunciation and receive real-time feedback[4]. Additionally, virtual classroom environments facilitated peer interactions, role-playing exercises, and language immersion experiences. Reading and writing skills were improved through AI-assisted text analysis tools, collaborative online writing platforms, and adaptive reading exercises. Pre-service teachers engaged with digital storytelling tools, automated grammar checkers, and online discussion forums. Observational data showed that teachers using digital tools engaged students more effectively, creating interactive lessons that personalized learning experiences. Furthermore, participants valued the flexibility and accessibility of digital resources but faced challenges such as technological limitations and institutional constraints[5].

The study's findings align with previous research suggesting that digital technologies develop integrated language skills by providing interactive, adaptive, and immersive learning experiences. The use of AI, gamification, and virtual learning environments has shown an effective result in improving linguistic proficiency and pedagogical skills. However, successful implementation demands structured training programs that concentrated on both digital literacy and pedagogical application. Without proper training, teachers may come across incorporate digital tools effectively, leading to passive or superficial use of technology in classrooms[6,7].

In today's era of developing educational technologies, some shortcomings in the organization of communication through Internet networks the emergence of problems related to the study of foreign languages in the educational process of students and the development of competencies in professional activity. It can b cause for obstacles [8].

Plus, it can be proven that a lack of access to advanced digital tools and stable internet connections. A portion of pre-service teachers exhibited reluctance to utilize new technologies, citing difficulties in adapting to digital platforms. Moreover, universities often lack structured digital training programs, requiring curriculum performs to provide technology integration[9].

Designing the lesson process with digital tools:

Ongoing digital literacy training	Universities should incorporate digital competency training as part of teacher education programs.
Use of AI-powered feedback systems	AI-driven applications can provide instant feedback on pronunciation, writing, and grammar, helping teachers and students improve language skills.
Gamification strategies	Digital games and interactive exercises enhance engagement and motivation among language learners.
Integration of virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR)	Immersive experiences facilitate authentic language practice, improving fluency and comprehension.

The issue of using modern technologies in the educational process is considered important. This is not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to learning. Our main goal is to improve the quality of teaching foreign language learners using modern technologies, improve their communicative culture, and show how technology can be effectively used for learning practical activities [10].

It discusses various approaches and methods that can help English language students improve their learning skills with the help of technology. In the course of research conducted by Abdullaeva B.S. a large part is devoted to highlighting the essence of the issue of technologization of activities aimed at training future personnel [11].

However, challenges such as technological accessibility and institutional resistance must be addressed to maximize the benefits of digital integration. Future

research should explore long-term impacts of digital methodologies in teacher training and investigate emerging technologies such as augmented reality and AI-driven personalized learning. For successful implementation, foreign language teacher education programs must prioritize structured digital literacy training, ensuring that pre-service teachers are equipped with the necessary skills to navigate modern language learning environments effectively.

It is worth noting that today, digital technology has already become a major teaching “tool” for teachers in developing students’ oral skills. A study has shown that the effectiveness of using various Internet technologies and information and communication tools, designing educational content, and developing practical exercises based on adequate adaptation to real-life problems for future teachers to speak English fluently [12].

In conclusion, this study highlights the effectiveness of digital technologies in developing integrated language skills among future foreign language teachers. By incorporating AI-powered applications, virtual classrooms, and gamified learning environments, teacher training programs can enhance linguistic proficiency and pedagogical competence.

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